

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE COURSE OF ISCHEMIC STROKE IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIAC PATHOLOGY IN THE STROKE CENTER OF ALMATY (KAZAKHSTAN)

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Abstract

In the stroke center of the multidisciplinary clinic in Almaty (Kazakhstan), for the period from 2019 to 2020, 774 patients with a clinical diagnosis of "Acute cerebrovascular accident" were treated. We analyzed 489 medical records of an inpatient with only a diagnosis of "Ischemic stroke"; of these, the average age was 65.5 ± 0.8 years, ischemic stroke predominated in women (1.4 times). We tried to identify the causes of ischemic stroke and found that, in general, of the admitted patients with ischemic stroke, it is ($63 \pm 2.6\%$), of which 84.04% fall on the share of cardiac pathology, which confirms the causes that often lead to acute ischemic strokes. As a result of the study, 411 patients were divided into groups due to the development of a stroke, namely, cardiac pathology. We have identified: the severity of ischemic stroke according to the NIHSS scale, and localization in the affected area. The increase in the proportion of elderly and senile people substantiates the need for special attention of neurologists and cardiologists, aggravating the severity of ischemic stroke and leading to complications such as thrombosis, recurrent strokes.

Keywords: ischemic stroke, acute cerebrovascular accident, cardiac arrhythmia, cerebrocardial syndrome, ischemic heart disease.

Relevance

Ischemic strokes in the structure of total mortality in Russia and Kazakhstan in the early recovery and long-term period account for a large share - 21.4%, with a tendency to early and long-term disability of the population from strokes. Mortality from stroke among people of working age has increased over the past 10 years by more than 30% (247.1 per 100,000 population) and tends to increase annually up to 3-4% [1, 2].

Stroke is an important medical and social problem. The most common type of stroke is a cerebral infarction. In this regard, in recent years, the system of care for this disease has been actively improved, mostly at the inpatient stage. The problem of acute cerebrovascular accident has become more acute due to a significant incidence of cardiac diseases and a high percentage of disability and mortality in diseases of the circulatory system [3, 4].

According to the official statistics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, more than 40 thousand cases of stroke are registered annually in the Republic of Kazakhstan, of which only 5 thousand die in the first 10 days and another 5 thousand within 1 month after discharge at home. Stroke is one of the main causes of disability in the adult population both in Kazakhstan and in the world [5, 6].

A high degree of correlation between an increase in the age of patients and an increase in the number of strokes has been proven, therefore, before the age of 60, a stroke occurs in a third of patients, two-thirds of acute cerebrovascular accidents occur in the age category

over 60 years. According to various authors, patients with ischemic brain damage die more often from cardiac causes than directly from acute cerebrovascular accident [7,8].

The purpose of the study: to identify patients with cardiac pathology who had ischemic stroke in the acute period and to analyze their course.

Material and methods

We analyzed the medical documentation (medical record of an inpatient patient - MRIP - further) in the stroke center of the city of Almaty (Republic of Kazakhstan) for the period from 2019 to 2020. During this period, a total of 774 patients with a clinical diagnosis of "Acute cerebrovascular accident" were treated: 489 ($63 \pm 2.6\%$) of them were patients with ischemic stroke, and 285 ($36.8 \pm 4.8\%$) patients with hemorrhagic stroke. Repeated ischemic strokes amounted to 24%.

Taking into account the anamnestic data of the admitted patients, it can be determined that this is mainly a cardiological pathology, because upon admission to a multidisciplinary clinic, all patients were consulted at the level of the admission department by a neurologist, therapist, neurosurgeon, who are part of the multidisciplinary team of the stroke center.

In the hospital, all patients with ischemic stroke were examined: CT/MRI of the brain to exclude/confirm stroke, echocardiography, ultrasound of the vessels of the head and neck, consultation of a therapist/cardiologist, neurosurgeon, laboratory tests according to the clinical protocol in force in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

As a result of the study, we divided the patients into groups due to the development of a stroke, namely, cardiac pathology.

We tried to determine the causes of ischemic stroke and found that most of the admitted patients had a history of cardiac pathology.

By age category, patients aged 50 to 80 years prevailed (mean age 65.5 ± 0.8 years), and by gender, ischemic stroke prevailed in women (by 1.4 times). Upon admission, all patients, along with basic therapy, are prescribed symptomatic treatment in accordance with the clinical protocol and those who have a concomitant disease.

Results

Among the patients analyzed by us, ischemic stroke developed for the first time in 77.5% of patients, and again in 24%.

Of 411 patients with acute ischemic stroke, cardiac diseases were identified: stenting - 46 (11.19%), coronary artery bypass grafting - 34 (8.27%), chronic coronary heart disease 2 B - 123 (29.92%), coronary heart disease, heart rhythm disturbance - 52 (12.65%), arterial hypertension 3 tbsp. - 115 (27.98%), condition after coronary angiography - 41 (9.97%).

Analyzing the medical records of inpatients with ischemic stroke, we identified the course and localization. Taking into account the classification based on pathophysiological signs according to the TOAST criteria, we analyzed cardiac embolisms and occlusions of small coronary vessels.

We present the results. Of our group of patients with ischemic stroke, cardiac embolism was detected in 38%, atherosclerosis of large arteries in 46.7%, and occlusion of small blood vessels in 11%. As for the localization of cerebral infarction, depending on the affected arterial pool, we got the following picture:

- vertebral arteries and their branches - 11%
- main artery and branches - 17%
- middle cerebral artery - 46%
- anterior cerebral artery - 4%
- posterior cerebral artery - 22%.

When patients were admitted to the clinic, we assessed the severity of the condition using the NIHSS scale and obtained the following data: moderate severity - 18 points - 11%;

- medium severity - 20 points - 27%;
- medium severity - 21 points - 34%;
- severe stroke - 22 points - 16%;
- severe stroke - 23 points - 12%.

From this, it follows that hemodynamic disturbances, a decrease in myocardial contractility and the presence of arrhythmia negatively affect the course of ischemic stroke in the acute period.

We see that 84% of patients with ischemic stroke ($63 \pm 2.6\%$) suffer from cardiological diseases, which are under the supervision of a cardiologist for a long time.

Of the treated patients with ischemic stroke after discharge from the hospital, only 68% are observed by general practitioners, although according to the documentation, doctors of the stroke center electronically transmit a notice of discharged patients to all clinics in Almaty.

Discussion

The MRIP analyzed by us confirmed that only 52% of patients were observed by a cardiologist, an endocrinologist at the place of attachment and are registered with a general practitioner at the dispensary. Consequently, not all patients timely control blood pressure and take antihypertensive therapy, as well as antiarrhythmic, anticoagulant, hypoglycemic drugs, etc.

This can be explained by the fact that people in this age group already have chronic diseases such as pathology of the cardiovascular system, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, high cholesterol, lipids, obesity and other diseases that are a provoking factor in the development of stroke, leading to ischemic stroke. In this category of patients, the severity of ischemic stroke is exacerbated by concomitant diseases. More attention is paid to such patients with cardiac arrhythmias (atrial fibrillation, extrasystole) (10.63%) and after CABG (6.95%), because This is an age group (70 years and older) and are more often accompanied by the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus, complicating the correction of hypoglycemic drugs and the selection of oral anticoagulants of indirect action. Therefore, this category of patients do not take indirect anticoagulants at home and do not control blood biochemical parameters.

As a result of our analysis of medical records (MRIP), we can conclude that more often cardiac diseases lead to ischemic stroke, so it remains one of the important problems not only for neurologists, but also for cardiologists, requiring special attention from the outpatient service.

Conclusions

Thus, the patients analyzed by us for the period 2019-2020 who had ischemic stroke in the acute period more often have cardiac diseases, which increases the high risks of complications and the severity of the course of the stroke itself. The proportion of elderly and senile people in the stroke center of Almaty for the period 2019-2020 is growing, which justifies the need for special attention to patients with cardiac pathology, which exacerbates the severity of ischemic stroke and leads to complications such as thrombosis, recurrent strokes.

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SOME EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DATA CONCERNING COLORECTAL CANCER IN THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Abstract

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common forms of malignant neoplasms in the world, which at the initial stage is almost asymptomatic, thereby making the process of diagnosing difficult. In the Republic of Belarus, over the past 10 years there has been a constant increase in the incidence of CRC.

This study analyzes the diagnostics, sickness and mortality rate from colorectal cancer in Minsk in 2016 and 2021 in different age groups of patients.

Keywords: colorectal cancer, symptoms, sickness rate, mortality rate, Minsk City Oncological dispensary, epidemiological data.

Introduction. In the structure of the incidence of oncological diseases, colorectal cancer (CRC) occupies one of the first positions. According to the official statistics of oncological diseases, in 2021 colorectal cancer (CRC) in Minsk ranked 2nd (16.1%), slightly second only to breast cancer (16.2%).

The purpose of this work is a comparative analysis of the sickness and mortality rate from colorectal cancer in Minsk based on various parameters.

Research materials and methods: the research material was the official statistical data of the Minsk City Clinical Dispensary on patients with colorectal cancer (CRC), collected at intervals of 5 years (for 2016 and 2021).

Results and discussion: The main risk factor for colorectal cancer in a formally healthy person is age [1]. Thus, the incidence of CRC in patients aged 40 years and younger is 8 cases per 100,000 of population,

and in people 60 years and older is 150 cases per 100,000 of population, and this applies to both men and women. 95% of patients with colorectal cancer in the UK are patients over 50 [2]. Of the 7 CIS countries, the highest sickness rate of CRC was registered in the Republic of Belarus, and the lowest in Uzbekistan.

According to the statistics of the Minsk City Clinical Dispensary, in 2016, CRC was first detected in 1,194 people (women – 52.7%; men – 47.3%), in 2021 – in 1,065 people (women – 48.5%; men – 51.5%). Thus, in 2016 and 2021, the diagnosis of CRC was made with approximately the same frequency for men and women. Using official statistics on the population in Minsk in 2016 (1,959,800) [3] and 2021 (2,009,786) [4], the incidence of CRC per 100,000 of population was calculated. In 2016, it was 60.9 cases, and in 2021 – 53.0.